

Nucleation studies in supersaturated aqueous solutions of thiourea doped with urea and urea nitrate

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Induction periods have been measured for various supersaturated aqueous solutions of thiourea doped with urea and urea nitrate separately by the direct vision method. Various critical nucleation parameters have been calculated based on classical theory for homogeneous crystal nucleation. For both the dopants, the critical nucleation parameters increase with the increase in concentration of doping in the thiourea solutions.

The thiourea (CH₄N₂S) crystal has orthorhombic structure with tetramolecular unit cell having the dimensions (ASTM file) : $a = 5.50$, $b = 7.68$ and $c = 8.57$ Å.

Nucleation process is the first and most important phenomenon in liquid-solid phase transition. This created considerable interest among research workers¹⁻⁶. Critical nucleation parameters like interfacial tension (σ) of the solid relative to its solution, energy of formation (ΔG) of a critical nucleus, and radius (r) of the critical nucleus can be calculated using the induction period (τ) which can be measured^{2,7,8}.

In order to understand the nucleation aspects, we have measured the induction periods for various supersaturated aqueous solutions of thiourea doped (impurity concentration in the range 2000–10000 ppm) with urea (CH₄N₂O) and urea nitrate (CH₄N₂.HNO₃) separately (impurity added in the aqueous solution of thiourea) in six different thiourea : dopant molecular ratios. The critical nucleation parameters have been calculated and the effect of supersaturation and concentration of doping on them is also reported.

Results and Discussion

The measured induction periods are presented in Table 1. For both the dopants, the value of τ decreases and hence the nucleation rate increases as the supersaturation and concentration of doping of the aqueous solution increase. This is similar to the earlier results^{3-6,8,9}.

Plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(S)$ (S is the supersaturation) are presented in Figs. 1 and 2. As per the classical theory for homogeneous crystal nucleation, linear plots are expected. However, we have observed deviation from linearity at lower supersaturation levels. Such deviation has

Table 1. Results of induction period measurements

Doping ratio	S^*	τ (s) for	
		Urea doped thiourea	Urea nitrate doped thiourea
Pure thiourea	1.60	1260	1260
	1.65	1080	1080
	1.70	900	900
	1.75	720	720
	1.80	600	600
	1.80	600	600
1 : 0.002	1.60	1080	960
	1.65	960	780
	1.70	780	600
	1.75	600	480
	1.80	480	360
	1.80	480	360
1 : 0.004	1.60	900	840
	1.65	840	600
	1.70	660	540
	1.75	480	420
	1.80	420	280
	1.80	420	280
1 : 0.006	1.60	780	720
	1.65	720	600
	1.70	540	480
	1.75	420	360
	1.80	360	240
	1.80	360	240
1 : 0.008	1.60	660	600
	1.65	600	480
	1.70	480	420
	1.75	360	300
	1.80	300	200
	1.80	300	200
1 : 0.010	1.60	540	480
	1.65	480	420
	1.70	390	360
	1.75	280	240
	1.80	210	180
	1.80	210	180

* Saturated concentration for thiourea is 1.729 M

Fig. 1. Plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/n^2(S)$ for urea doped thiourea

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/n^2(S)$ for urea nitrate doped thiourea

been previously reported^{3,4,6,7,9,10} and explained by considering the heterogeneous nucleation caused by the unwanted impurity particles present in the aqueous solution. The linear relationship is expected at higher supersaturations because the effect of the natural impurity particles present in the solvent is dominated by the presence of greater amount of solute. Also, the linear dependence is more when the solubility of the substance is more. The higher solubility component may dominate over the unwanted impurities present in the solvent in a better way than that in the case of substance with lower solubility as it was observed with $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (lower solubility and less linear dependence) and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (higher solubility and more linear dependence)¹⁰.

Considering the principles of homogeneous and heterogeneous nucleation theories, the free energy of formation of a nucleus under heterogeneous nucleation is less than that of a homogeneous condition⁷.

The effect of solvent impurities cannot be reduced by increasing the supersaturation because the maximum practical limit for the measurement of induction period does not allow the supersaturation to exceed 1.80. If the supersaturation is beyond the practical limit, then nucleation occurs before the attainment of supersaturation. Hence, in order to reduce the effect of these practical difficulties on the nucleation parameters, the present results were obtained using the slope determined in the linear region of the plots.

The nucleation parameters are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 3. Dependence of energy of formation of critical nucleus on supersaturation for urea doped thiourea

Fig. 4. Dependence of energy of formation of critical nucleus on supersaturation for urea nitrate doped thiourea

Fig. 5. Dependence of radius of critical nucleus on supersaturation for urea doped thiourea

Fig. 6. Dependence of radius of critical nucleus on supersaturation for urea nitrate doped thiourea.

The values of ΔG and r at various supersaturations have also been calculated for all the crystals and the results are presented in Figs. 3-6. It was observed that the values of ΔG and r decrease when the supersaturation increases. This

result is similar to that observed by previous authors. For both the dopants considered in the present study, it can be seen from Table 2 and Figs. 3-6 that the critical nucleation parameters (σ , ΔG and r) increase with the increase in concentration of doping in the thiourea solution. Similar results were observed for the dopants KBr, K_2CrO_4 , and $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in the case of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate (KDP)^{11,12} and for the dopants KCl, $(NH_4)_2SO_4$, K_2SO_4 , $(NH_4)_2C_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$, NaCl and $NaH_2PO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ in the case of ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate (ADP)³⁻⁶.

Table 2. Nucleation parameters*

Doping ratio	Urea doped thiourea			Urea nitrate doped thiourea		
	σ mJ m ⁻²	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	r nm	σ mJ m ⁻²	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	r nm
Pure thiourea	6.381	3.473	0.464	6.381	3.473	0.464
1 : 0.002	6.653	3.935	0.484	6.995	4.574	0.509
1 : 0.004	6.740	4.091	0.490	7.230	5.051	0.526
1 : 0.006	6.782	4.170	0.500	7.291	5.179	0.531
1 : 0.008	6.850	4.295	0.508	7.390	5.393	0.538
1 : 0.010	6.983	4.349	0.511	7.450	5.525	0.542

* ΔG and r values calculated at the maximum supersaturation

Rachelin and Mahadevan³ attempted to explain qualitatively the variation of nucleation parameters with doping concentration in the case of ADP by considering the densities of the dopants. The nucleation parameters increase with doping concentration for the denser dopants and decrease with the doping concentration for the rarer dopants. Later, it was found that all the doped crystals except $(NH_4)_2C_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ and $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ doped ADP hold this density rule. Hence, it was attempted to say⁵ that, for an inorganic substance like ADP and KDP the nucleation parameters increase with doping concentration for the dopants having higher density and high or equal (molecular) weight cation and decrease with the doping concentration for the dopants having lower density and low or equal (molecular) weight cation.

In the case of $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ added (as impurities) $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, it was found⁸ that the nucleation parameters decrease with the increase in concentration of $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ addition and increase with the increase in concentration of $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ addition in the $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ solution. This variation could not be explained using the above density rules. As $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ are isomorphous to $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, a qualitative explanation was attempted by considering the lattice volumes or molecular volumes of the impurities. The nucleation parameters increase with the impurity concentration for the impurity with larger lattice and decrease with the impurity concentration for the impurity with smaller lattice.

The results observed in the present study cannot be ex-

plained by the above density and lattice volume rules. As the systems considered in the present study are organic compounds, we may attribute the variation of nucleation parameters with doping concentration to the unpredictable situation caused by the impurities. However, the exact reason for this is not understood.

Experimental

Thiourea, urea and other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used. Urea nitrate was prepared by following the reported procedure¹³. Aqueous solutions of various supersaturated concentrations were prepared by dissolving the required amounts of thiourea and the dopant at temperatures slightly higher than the saturation temperature. Supersaturation was obtained by natural cooling.

Induction periods were measured following the reported procedures^{4,8}. Experiments were performed with five selected supersaturations, viz. 1.60, 1.65, 1.70, 1.75 and 1.80 at 33.5°. Volume of solutions taken in the nucleation cell was maintained at 20 ml in all the experiments. Several nucleation runs were carried out under controlled and unstirred conditions. Reproducible results were obtained within an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$. The supersaturated concentration considered provided an induction period of at least 150 s. Various critical nucleation parameters were calculated following the reported procedures⁴.

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